

THE MULTIPLE INTELLIGENCES OF PRIMARY PUPILS OF SAINT FERDINAND COLLEGE AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP TO ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AS BASIS FOR DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTIONAL ACTIVITIES

May–Ann M. Nicolas
Marites P. Talosig

Saint Ferdinand College-City of Ilagan Campus, City of Ilagan, Isabela, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19256055>

ABSTRACT

This study explores the multiple intelligences (MI) of primary pupils at Saint Ferdinand College and examines their relationship with academic performance, aiming to provide a basis for differentiated instructional activities. The research identified the varying strengths in pupils, which include bodily-kinesthetic, musical, logico-mathematical, interpersonal, intrapersonal, verbal-linguistic, and visual-spatial intelligences. By examining the profiles of the respondents—age, sex, and availability of educational materials at home—the study sought to determine how these factors influence MI development and academic outcomes. The research employed a descriptive methodology, utilizing statistical tools like frequency distribution, percentage analysis, and Chi-square tests to assess the relationship between MIs and academic performance. Results showed that multiple intelligences are independent of age, sex, and availability of educational materials. However, significant relationships were found between academic performance and age, as well as access to educational materials at home. The study concluded that understanding and aligning teaching strategies with pupils' dominant intelligences enhances academic achievement. Teachers are encouraged to adopt differentiated instructional activities to nurture diverse intellectual strengths, and further research is recommended to explore other influencing factors.

Keywords: *Multiple Intelligences, Academic Performance, Differentiated Instruction, Primary Pupils, Educational Materials*

INTRODUCTION

Education is a basic human right that supports individual growth, empowerment, and success (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO], 2020). Education needs to be encompassing, extending beyond academics, shaping learners intellectually, emotionally, socially, and creatively, rather than a one-size-fits-all system. Education that is meaningful and individualized fosters each learner's unique talents, interests, and full potential (Gardner, 2011). It embraces the philosophy that all children, regardless of race, background, physical attributes, abilities, or disabilities, deserve equal access to quality education (UNESCO, 2020).

Every child is considered to be unique in terms of how they think, learn, and achieve academically. Pupils have a variety of strengths—some excel at math, while others express themselves using words, music, or movement. Multiple Intelligences (MI) suggest that intelligence comes in various forms, including skills with words, numbers, images, music, social interaction, self-awareness, and physical movement. This idea challenges the traditional thinking of intelligence being a single ability, emphasizing that each person possesses a unique combination of multiple intelligences, with some being more dominant than others (Gardner, 2011). Understanding these multiple intelligences is crucial for shaping effective teaching strategies (Gardner, 2011). For teachers to know what teaching methods, strategies, and techniques to utilize for a diverse group of pupils, teachers must first determine the multiple intelligences and learning styles of the pupils to improve teaching strategies when teaching a lesson (Armstrong, 2017).

The term “intelligence” refers to a general mental capacity focusing on reasoning, problem-solving, and abstract thinking, which is why society has traditionally prioritized traditional academic brilliance, as intelligence has predominantly been assessed by proficiency in mathematics and language. Individuals who excel in other fields, such as music, athletics, sketching, and the arts, are given minimal recognition. MI highlights that all types of intelligence are equally important and encourages both teachers and pupils to recognize and develop each individual's strengths, rather than focusing solely on traditional academic skills (Gardner, 2011).

Aligning teaching strategies with pupils' intelligence and learning style allows them to reach their full academic potential (Armstrong, 2017). Identifying one's intelligence is relevant for teachers as it allows them to adapt, provide differentiated educational activities, and devise a classroom layout that caters to student diversity (Gardner, 2011).

In the researcher's three years of teaching experience, it has been consistently observed that pupils exhibit diverse intellectual profiles, as she observed each pupil demonstrates unique strengths and talents across different domains and differs in how they absorb and respond to instruction. She noticed that some of her pupils excel in logical and problem-solving, while others learn more effectively through music and sound. Additionally, some pupils thrive in social settings and collaborate well in groups, whereas others prefer to learn independently. Furthermore, she noticed that children perform better when learning activities match their strengths, such as art, movement, or group work (Armstrong, 2017).

For this reason, the researcher pursued this study on multiple intelligences, believing that it offers an effective approach to meeting the diverse needs of learners, as she believes that providing appropriate and varied teaching and learning activities is essential in addressing individual differences, and this kind of approach has the potential to enhance pupils' academic performance.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the multiple intelligences of primary pupils of Saint Ferdinand College and examined their effect on academic performance. It sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. Age
 - b. Sex
 - c. Availability of Educational Materials at Home
2. What is the dominant intelligences of the respondents?
3. What is the academic performance of the respondents?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the multiple intelligences of the respondents when grouped according to their profiles?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the academic performance of the respondents and their profiles?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' multiple intelligences and their academic performance?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher employed the descriptive research method. This method described the characteristics of the variables and help give a clear understanding of the thesis topic. This methodology were used to describe, explain, and interpret characteristics of a population or situation, it focuses on answering questions relating to "what" than the "why" of the thesis topic.

This research method helped the researcher to identify the profiles and the multiple intelligences of the primary pupils of Saint Ferdinand College and examine the relationship of the MIs to academic performance, it also ensured that all data collected were accurate and reliable.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted at Saint Ferdinand College- Ilagan Campus. Saint Ferdinand College is a private Catholic educational institution established in 1950. For 75 years, SFC has had a long-standing tradition of academic excellence and character formation, offering programs from Basic Education to Graduate School studies. The SFC

Elementary Department is dedicated to providing a quality and holistic education for young learners and is proud to be Level II accredited under the PACUCOA accreditation, reflecting its commitment to academic excellence and continuous improvement. The SFC-main campus is located at Santa Ana Street, Barangay Bagumbayan, City of Ilagan, Isabela.

Selection and Description of Respondents

The 111 respondents of the study were the primary pupils currently enrolled at Saint Ferdinand College for the S.Y 2024-2025.

**Table 1
Total Population**

GRADE AND SECTION	RESPONDENTS
Grade 1 – St. Joseph	20
Grade 1 – St. Valentine	21
Grade 2 – St. Anastasia	28
Grade 3 – St. Barbara	20
Grade 3 – St. Matilda	22
TOTAL:	111

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher wrote a formal letter to the President of the institution requesting permission to conduct the study. To obtain the necessary data, the researcher sought approval from the principal of the SFC Elementary Department to distribute the questionnaire and was administered in person, and the respondents' grades were collected from their advisers. After gathering all required data, the researcher tallied, tabulated, and analyzed the results.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data treated statistically using the following:

Frequency and percentage distribution. This was used to determine the profile of the respondents, to analyze the multiple intelligences of the respondents and for the academic performance of the respondents.

Chi-Square-Test. This was used to determine if there was a significant relationship between the multiple intelligences of the respondents when grouped according to their profiles.

It was also used to determine if there was a significant relationship between the academic performance of the respondents and their profiles.

Additionally, it was used to determine if there was a significant relationship between the respondents' multiple intelligences and their academic performance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. What is the profile of the pupils in terms of

a. Age

Table 2
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Pupils in Terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percent
5-6 years old	22	19.8
7-8 Years old	67	60.4
9-10 Years old	22	19.8
Total	111	100.0

Table 2 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the pupils in terms of age.

Among the 111 respondents, the largest group is aged 7-8 years, accounting for 60.4% of the total. This is followed by respondents aged 5-6 years and 9-10 years, both accounting for 19.8% each.

According to DepEd Order No. 015, s.2025, the ages of most respondents fall within the ideal age range for primary pupils (Kindergarten to Grade 3) in the Philippines. The policy states that pupils should start Kindergarten at least five years old by October 31 of the school year. Consequently, a 7–8-year-old child is typically in Grade 2 or Grade 3. However, a small portion of the pupils are 10 years old, slightly exceed the typical age range.

b. Sex

Table 3
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Pupils in Terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Male	55	49.5
Female	56	50.5
Total	111	100.0

Table 3 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the pupils in terms of sex.

Out of 111 pupils, 56 or 50.5% are female and 49.5% are male. This means that the number of female pupils is slightly higher than that of male pupils. However, the

difference is very small, showing that there is almost an equal number of boys and girls as respondents.

The data shows that majority of the pupils are female which conform with the general observation that in many schools, private or public that there is almost equal distribution.

The findings support the findings of Bautista (2015) which revealed that there are more female students, who are predominantly interpersonal intelligent. Meanwhile, a study conducted by Limon (2021) negates the results of the study who revealed that there are more male than female students.

c. Availability of Educational Materials at Home

Table 4 .1
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the pupils in terms of Availability of Gadgets at Home

GADGETS	Frequency	Percent
Smartphone	78	70.27
Tablet / iPad	66	59.46
Laptop / Desktop Computers	54	48.65
Television	85	76.58
DVD / CD Player	13	11.71
Other/s: Projector	1	0.90

Table 3.1 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the pupils in terms of the availability of educational materials at home, specifically classified as gadgets.

The result reveal that among the listed gadgets, television and smartphone are the most commonly owned devices, with 85 pupils or 76.58% and 78 pupils or 70.27% respectively. On the other hand, the DVD/CD player and projector are the least owned gadgets, with only 13 pupils or 11.71% and 1 pupil or 0.90% respectively.

This shows that most families have easy access to gadgets for entertainment, communication, and learning. It also means that other gadgets are now less common at home because of new technologies. This means that technology is becoming more important in children's learning.

The findings above supports the study of del Moral-Perez et al. (2015) as they explored suitable video games at home and their systematic use to promote the development of multiple intelligences among primary pupils. Moreover, a study conducted by Da-anton and Dioso (2025) revealed that electronic gadgets are commonly used among students and emphasized the importance of parents and teachers to guide students in using gadgets more purposefully.

Table 4.2
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the pupils in terms of Availability of Books at Home

BOOKS	Frequency	Percent
Storybooks	72	64.86
Alphabet / Phonic Books	40	36.04
Dictionary	27	24.32
Encyclopedia	8	7.21
Reading Comprehension Books	39	35.14
Writing Practice Books	40	36.04
Art Books	74	66.67
Math Activity Books	52	46.85
Other/s: Bible	11	9.91

Table 4.2 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the pupils in terms of the availability of educational materials at home, specifically classified as books.

The data reveal that art books and storybooks are the most commonly owned, with 74 pupils or 66.67% and 72 pupils or 64.86% respectively. In contrast, the encyclopedia and dictionary are the least owned books, with only 8 pupils or 7.21% and 27 pupils or 24.32% respectively. Additionally, Bible was also mentioned, with 11 pupils or 9.91% owning one at home.

The results of the study showed that pupils have access to reading resources, but the type and number of books they have at home vary. Many pupils owned creative and imaginative books that help improve their art and reading skills. However, reference books, such as dictionaries and encyclopedias are less common, possibly because they are more advanced, costly or less engaging for young pupils.

The findings of the study negate the study of Ezeanwu et al. (2022) who revealed that most primary school pupils do not have access to reading resources while participating in learning activities at home, and children are exposed to poor modeled reading behavior.

Table 4.3
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the pupils in terms of Availability of Musical Instruments at Home

MUSICAL INSTRUMENTS	Frequency	Percent
Piano	43	38.74
Guitar	50	45.05
Ukelele	19	17.12
Tambourine	10	9.01
Xylophone	23	20.72
Drums	29	26.13

Violin	6	5.41
Other/s: Flute	2	1.80
Other/s: Maracas	1	0.90

Table 4.3 presented the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents according to the availability of educational materials at home, specifically classified as Musical Instruments.

The data reveal that guitar and piano are the most commonly owned musical instruments, with 50 pupils or 45.05% and 43 pupils or 38.74% respectively. Meanwhile, the maracas and flute are the least owned instruments, with only 1 pupil 0.90% and 2 pupils or 1.80% owned it respectively. This suggest that pupils are more likely to have instruments that are accessible. Meanwhile, instruments like flute and maracas are less common because they are not as popular, are more challenging to learn or play, and are considered less practical for home use.

The findings support the study conducted by Politimou et al. (2018) who states that majority of children show spontaneous enjoyment of singing, being exposed to music and interacting with musical instruments at home contribute to developmental outcomes. Furthermore, a study conducted by Blasco-Magraner et al. (2021) suggest several beneficial effects of music on children's development, such as greater emotional intelligence, academic performance and prosocial skills.

Table 4.4
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the pupils in terms of Availability of Games or Toys at Home

GAMES / TOYS WITH EDUCATIONAL VALUE	Frequency	Percent
Puzzles	50	45.05
LEGO / Building Blocks	80	72.07
Flashcards	38	34.23
Board Games	56	50.45
Toy Globe or Map	28	25.23

Table 4.4 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents according to the availability of educational materials at home, specifically classified as Games or Toys with Educational Value.

The data reveal that Lego or building blocks and board games are the most common educational toys at home, 80 pupils or 72.07 % and 56 pupils or 50.45% respectively. In contrast, globe or map and flashcards are the least common, with 28 pupils or 25.23% and 38 pupils or 34.23% respectively.

The results of the study reveal that the respondents have different types of toys or games with educational value available in their home. Lego, building blocks, and puzzles are toys that are popular because they are fun, it promotes focus, creativity, and help

develop problem-solving skills. On the other side, globe or map and flashcards are less common because they are more used for study than play, making them less appealing to young pupils.

The data supports the idea of Dag et al. (2021) who states that games and toys are important for the child to be part of society as healthy individual at every stage of his development.

2. What are the dominant intelligences of the respondents?

Table 5
The Dominant Intelligences of the Grade 1 Pupils

Code	Dominant Intelligence/s	F	%
1	Bodily-Kinesthetic Intelligence	9	21.95
2	Interpersonal Intelligence	3	7.32
3	Intrapersonal Intelligence	2	4.88
4	Logico-Mathematical Intelligence	5	12.20
5	Musical Intelligence	8	19.51
6	Verbal-Linguistic Intelligence	1	2.44
7	Visual-Spatial Intelligence	3	7.32
14	Bodily-Kinesthetic Intelligence & Logico-Mathematical Intelligence	1	2.44
15	Bodily-Kinesthetic Intelligence & Musical Intelligence	2	4.88
35	Intrapersonal Intelligence & Musical Intelligence	1	2.44
45	Logico-Mathematical Intelligence & Musical Intelligence	1	2.44
46	Logico-Mathematical Intelligence & Verbal-Linguistic Intelligence	1	2.44
47	Logico-Mathematical Intelligence & Visual-Spatial Intelligence	1	2.44
126	Bodily-Kinesthetic Intelligence & Interpersonal Intelligence & Verbal-Linguistic Intelligence	1	2.44
135	Bodily-Kinesthetic Intelligence & Intrapersonal Intelligence & Musical Intelligence	1	2.44
145	Bodily-Kinesthetic Intelligence & Logico-Mathematical Intelligence & Musical Intelligence	1	2.44
	Total	41	100.00

Table 5 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the dominant intelligences of the Grade 1 pupils.

It reveals that the respondents have different dominant intelligences. Some have only one dominant intelligence, while others possess two or three dominant intelligences. There are nine or 21.95% have Bodily-Kinesthetic Intelligence as their dominant intelligence. This followed by Musical Intelligence, with eight or 19.51%, and Logico-Mathematical Intelligence, with five or 12.20%. In addition, there are 3 or 7.32% have Interpersonal Intelligence and Visual-Spatial Intelligence as their dominant intelligences.

Meanwhile, two or 4.88% exhibit Intrapersonal Intelligence as their dominant intelligence. Only one or 2.44% demonstrates Verbal-Linguistic as a dominant intelligence. The remaining respondents, each comprising 2.44%, show two or three intelligence combinations as their dominant intelligences.

The results of the study are supported by Gardner (2013), who proposes that intelligence is diverse and multifaceted which means that people have different types of intellectual strengths. Similarly, Nisa et al., (2025) supports the findings of the present study, reporting that Bodily-Kinesthetic intelligence was the most dominant among the students. Gardner further characterizes individuals with bodily-kinesthetic intelligence as “body smart”. In contrast, the findings differ from the study of Mufit (2022) which revealed that Visual-Spatial intelligence was the most dominant intelligence type among respondents.

Table 6
The Dominant Intelligences of the Grade 2 Pupils

Code	Dominant Intelligence/s	F	%
1	Bodily-Kinesthetic Intelligence	6	21.43
2	Interpersonal Intelligence	1	3.57
4	Logico-Mathematical Intelligence	2	7.14
5	Musical Intelligence	8	28.57
6	Verbal-Linguistic Intelligence	2	7.14
7	Visual-Spatial Intelligence	5	17.86
14	Bodily-Kinesthetic Intelligence & Logico-Mathematical Intelligence	1	3.57
35	Intrapersonal Intelligence & Musical Intelligence	1	3.57
136	Bodily-Kinesthetic Intelligence & Intrapersonal Intelligence & Verbal-Linguistic Intelligence	1	3.57
157	Bodily-Kinesthetic Intelligence & Musical Intelligence & Visual-Spatial Intelligence	1	3.57
	Total	28	100.00

Table 6 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the dominant intelligences of the Grade 2 pupils.

The data reveal that eight or 28.57% have Musical Intelligence as their dominant intelligence, followed by Bodily-Kinesthetic Intelligence with six or 21.43%, and Visual-Spatial Intelligence with five or 17.86%. Meanwhile, two or 7.14% exhibit Logico-Mathematical Intelligence and Verbal-Linguistic Intelligence as their dominant intelligences. Other intelligences, such as Interpersonal Intelligence and combinations of two to three dominant intelligences each possessed by one or 3.57%.

The findings of the study are consistent with Gardner’s (2013) Theory of Multiple Intelligences, which asserts that individuals exhibit varying levels of different intelligences. Similarly, Dela Cruz (2013) found that respondents predominantly exhibited musical

intelligence. Gardner further characterizes individuals with musical intelligence as “music smart”. In contrast, Doblson (2022) reported that musical intelligence was the least manifested among respondents.

Table 7
The Dominant Intelligences of the Grade 3 Pupils

Code	Dominant Intelligence/s	F	%
1	Bodily-Kinesthetic Intelligence	6	14.29
2	Interpersonal Intelligence	6	14.29
3	Intrapersonal Intelligence	5	11.90
4	Logico-Mathematical Intelligence	2	4.76
5	Musical Intelligence	11	26.19
6	Verbal-Linguistic Intelligence	2	4.76
7	Visual-Spatial Intelligence	1	2.38
12	Bodily-Kinesthetic Intelligence & Interpersonal Intelligence	2	4.76
13	Bodily-Kinesthetic Intelligence & Intrapersonal Intelligence	1	2.38
16	Bodily-Kinesthetic Intelligence & Verbal-Linguistic Intelligence	1	2.38
23	Interpersonal Intelligence & Intrapersonal Intelligence	1	2.38
25	Interpersonal Intelligence & Musical Intelligence	1	2.38
26	Interpersonal Intelligence & Verbal-Linguistic Intelligence	1	2.38
36	Intrapersonal Intelligence & Visual-Spatial Intelligence	1	2.38
67	Verbal-Linguistic Intelligence & Visual-Spatial Intelligence	1	2.38
	Total	42	100.00

Table 7 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the dominant intelligences of the Grade 3 pupils.

There are eleven or 26.19% who have Musical Intelligence as their dominant intelligence. In addition, six or 14.29% each have Bodily-Kinesthetic Intelligence and Interpersonal Intelligence as their dominant intelligences. Meanwhile, five or 11.90% demonstrate Intrapersonal Intelligence as their dominant intelligence. Furthermore, two or 4.76% each have Logico-Mathematical Intelligence, Verbal-Linguistic Intelligence, and a combination of Bodily-Kinesthetic and Interpersonal Intelligences as their dominant intelligences. Other intelligences, such as Visual-spatial Intelligence and combinations of two to three dominant intelligences each possessed by one respondent or 2.38%.

The findings of the study are anchored on the theory of Gardner (2023), which states that individuals differ in distinct intellectual abilities, this means that all people possess multiple intelligences, and no two individuals have the same intellectual profile. However, the findings of the present study partially contradict the study of Harhatik et al., (2021) which revealed that students possess a dominant interpersonal intelligence, the findings of this study show that Musical Intelligence is the primary dominant intelligence among respondents, and interpersonal and Bodily-Kinesthetic intelligences tied for the second-highest ranking, rather than being the most dominant.

3. What is the academic performance of the respondents?

Table 8
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents Academic Performance of the Respondents

Academic Performance	Grading Scales	Frequency (f)	Percent (%)
Outstanding	90-100	61	55.0
Very Satisfactory	85-89	36	32.4
Satisfactory	80-84	13	11.7
Fairly Satisfactory	75-79	1	.9
Did Not Meet Expectations	Below 75	0	0
Total		111	100.0

Table 6 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the academic performance of the respondents.

The data reveal the academic performance of 111 pupils enrolled in the S.Y 2024-2025. The majority or 61 pupils or 55.0%, were rated as Outstanding, while one pupil or 0.90% with Fairly Satisfactory grade. Interestingly, no pupils fell under Did Not Meet Expectations. Thus, the pupils showed that they are doing well in their studies.

The data above is different from the study conducted by Capinding (2021) whose study revealed that there are 7.69% who had outstanding grade, 61.64% who had fair grades and 30.77% satisfactory grades. In contrast, the present study noted that there are more respondents who achieved outstanding grades.

4. Is there a significant relationship between multiple intelligences of the respondents when grouped according to their profiles?

Table 9
Results on the Significant Relationship between the Multiple Intelligences of the Respondents and Their Profile

Profile	Significance χ^2	Decision	Remarks
Age	.060	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Sex	.094	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Availability of Educational Materials at Home	.727	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Table 9 shows the significant relationship between the multiple intelligences of the respondents and their profile using Chi-square-test at .05 level of significance.

As shown, the significance χ^2 -values for profile age, sex, grade level and availability of educational materials at home were greater than .05 which resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. There is no significant relationship between the multiple intelligences of the respondents and their profile age, sex, grade level and availability of educational materials at home. Thus, age, sex, grade level and availability of educational materials at home are independent variables that do not stimulate the multiple intelligences of the learners.

This implies that multiple intelligences are maybe influence by other factors such as individual ways of learning experiences and natural talents rather than by age, sex, and home resources. Likewise, having educational materials at home may support learning but it does not directly translate to stronger MI's emphasizing the need for active, engaging classroom experiences to develop, enhance, and strengthen each type of intelligences.

According to the study of Dela Cruz (2013) whose results support the findings of the present study, no significant differences were observed in the perception of multiple intelligences when grouped according to profile variables such as age, sex, parents' educational attainment, occupation, and family income.

Moreover, the findings of the present study contradict the study of Nulhakim and Berlian (2020), who investigated 71 primary pupils divided into an experimental group of male students and a controlled group of female students. Their study revealed that male students score higher in visual-spatial, musical, logico-mathematical, interpersonal, and bodily-kinesthetic intelligences, while female students excelled in verbal-linguistic and interpersonal intelligences. These findings suggest that sex may influence the development of certain intelligences.

5. Is there a significant relationship between the academic performance of the respondents and their profiles?

Table 10
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship between the Academic Performance of the Respondents and Their Profiles

Profile	Significance χ^2	Decision	Remarks
Age	.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Sex	.281	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Availability of Educational Materials at Home	.029	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 8 shows the test of significant relationship between the academic performance of the respondents and their profile using Chi-square-test at .05 level of significance.

As shown, the significance χ^2 -value for profile sex was greater than .05 which resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. There is no significant relationship between the academic performance of the respondents and their profile sex. Thus, sex is a variable that do not influence the academic performance of the learners.

For the profile age and availability of educational materials at home; the significance χ^2 -value for profile sex were less than .05 which resulted to the rejection of the null hypothesis. There is significant relationship between the academic performance of the respondents and their profile age, and availability of educational materials at home. Thus, age and availability of educational materials at home are variables that do influence the academic performance of the learners.

This means that age, grade level and availability of educational materials at home affects the academic performance of the learners; particularly those who are 7-8 years old, and with more educational materials at Home. This means that pupils' performance improves as they get older, it also indicates that pupils who have access to books, and other educational resources tend to perform better in school. Thus, it is important for teachers, parents and guardians to give proper learning support and materials to help their children.

The present study supports the findings of who revealed that factors such as students' parental levels of education and income, textbooks availability and accessibility, libraries, practical laboratory, meals provision and teachers have tremendous effects on the academic performance of students at school. However, the findings of the present study contradict the findings of Capinding (2021), which showed that age, sex, educational environment have no direct relationship with academic performance among primary students.

6. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' multiple intelligences and their academic performance by Grade level?

Table 11
Results on the Significant Relationship between the Multiple Intelligences and Academic Performance of the Respondents by Grade Level

Grade Level	Group	Significance χ^2	Decision	Remarks
Grade 1	Multiple Intelligences And Academic Performance	No statistics are computed.	None	Academic Performance is Constant

Grade 2	Multiple Intelligences And Academic Performance	.113	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Grade 3	Multiple Intelligences And Academic Performance	.002	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 10 shows the significant relationship between respondents' multiple intelligences and their academic performance by grade level using Chi-square-test at .05 level of significance.

As shown, the significance χ^2 -value for the group multiple intelligences and academic performance of Grade 1 respondents cannot be computed since the academic performance of the respondents is constant hence a relationship could not be determined because all Grade 1 respondents had the same academic performance score.

For Grade 2 respondents, the significance χ^2 -value between multiple intelligences and academic performance was greater than .05 which resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. There is no significant relationship between respondents' multiple intelligences and their academic performance. Thus, multiple intelligences and academic performance of the learners are independent with each other; hence, both variables do not influence each other.

For Grade 3 respondents, the significance χ^2 -value between multiple intelligences and academic performance was less than .05 which resulted to the rejection of the null hypothesis. There is significant relationship between respondents' multiple intelligences and the academic performance of Grade 3 respondents.

Results indicate that relationships between multiple intelligences and academic performance of the respondents are independent with each other in Grade 2 while dependent with each other in Grade 3. Hence, both variables were significantly observed to influence each other in Grade 3 Level.

The findings of the study are partially supported by Ibrahim and Al Saeed (2017), who reported a significant positive correlation between multiple intelligences and academic performance. Their findings align with the findings of the present study for Grade 3 pupils, where pupils with higher MI scores tends to perform academically. However, the findings of Dela Cruz (2013) which revealed a slight negative correlation between multiple intelligence and academic performance.

These contrasting findings highlight that the relationship between multiple intelligences and academic performance may vary depending on the grade level, which

aligns with the present study where Grade 2 showed no relationship while Grade 3 exhibited a significant relationship.

Table 12
Results on the Significant Relationship between the Multiple Intelligences and Academic Performance of the Respondents

Group	Significance χ^2	Decision	Remarks
Multiple Intelligences And Academic Performance	.000	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 12 shows the significant relationship between respondents' multiple intelligences and their academic performance using Chi-square-test at .05 level of significance.

As shown, the significance χ^2 -value for the group multiple intelligences and academic performance of respondents was less than .05 which resulted to the rejection of the null hypothesis. There is significant relationship between respondents' multiple intelligences and their academic performance. Thus, multiple intelligences and academic performance of the learners are dependent with each other; hence, both variables do influence with each other.

This implies that the respondents' multiple intelligences are associated with how well they perform academically. Pupils who exhibit strengths in specific intelligences tend to demonstrate better academic outcomes when learning experiences are aligned with their dominant intelligences. This finding highlights the importance of recognizing individual differences in learners and to incorporate diverse instructional strategies where pupils will likely to engage actively and achieve higher academic performance.

The study of Yavich and Rotnitsky (2020) supports the findings of the present study, as they concluded that the presence of dominant intelligences can predict and indicate student success. Moreover, Ahvan and Pour (2016) also supports the findings of the study, who found that multiple intelligences, including the logico-mathematical, visual-spatial, verbal-linguistic, intrapersonal, bodily-kinesthetic intelligences are positively linked to students' academic performance.

Conclusions

The study on the multiple intelligences of primary pupils of Saint Ferdinand College and their relationship to academic performance as a basis for differentiated instructional activities revealed that the respondents are diverse and unique individuals, each with varied dominant intelligences.

The findings show that pupils' multiple intelligences are not significantly influenced by their age, sex, or the availability of educational materials at home, indicating that these factors alone do not determine the development of MI. Sex also did not significantly affect academic performance, however, age and availability of educational materials at home were found to have a significant relationship with academic performance, suggesting that maturity and available resources support learning of the pupils. Moreover, the study found that the relationship between multiple intelligences and academic performance varied according to grade level. In Grade 1, the relationship could not be computed because all pupils obtained the same academic scores. In Grade 2, there was no significant relationship between multiple intelligences and academic performance, which means that the two variables were independent to each other. In contrast, Grade 3 pupils showed a significant relationship between MI's and academic performance, which suggested that pupils with higher MI scores tends to perform better academically.

Thus, multiple intelligences were associated with academic performance and it highlights the importance of using differentiated instructional activities that considers pupils' unique intelligences to enhance learning and maximize their strengths.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion of the study the following are recommended:

1. Everyone must consider learner diversity. Teachers need to identify the multiple intelligences of their pupils as basis for integrating MI-based teaching strategies and constructing differentiated instructional plan that composed of varied activities necessary in strengthening and enhancing the multiple intelligences. Teachers are encouraged to provide meaningful and active learning experiences that will nurture and strengthen multiple intelligences of the pupils.

Table 13
Sample of Differentiated Instructional Activities by Grade Level

Multiple Intelligences	Grade 1	Grade 2	Grade 3
Bodily-Kinesthetic Intelligence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role Playing • Dramatization (Simple Scenarios) • Physical Activities (Jumping, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role playing • Dramatization • Physical activities • Dancing • Playing sports 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role playing • Dramatization • Tableau • Sports games (basketball, volleyball, badminton)

	<p>Rolling, Crawling)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dancing • Playing Simple sports games • Follow the leader movements • Movement-based games (Simon Says, Red Light-Green Light games) • Letter and Number Formation Using Body Movements • Action Songs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simulations • Tableau • Hands on activities (clay, cardboard construction, popsicle sticks) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simulations • Hands-on activities (woodworking, clay, cardboard construction) • Letter and number formation using body movements
Musical Intelligence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Singing • Clapping and Tapping Rhythms • Sound Imitation • Tempo Games 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Playing musical instruments • Writing songs or putting poems to music • Super memory music • Music concepts • Singing • Chanting • Rapping 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Playing various musical instruments • Writing original songs/poems to music • Super memory music and music concepts • Singing • Chanting • Rapping

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clapping and tapping rhythms • Tempo games
Verbal-Linguistic Intelligence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Listening to and answering simple questions about stories • Role-Playing simple dialogues • Oral sharing • Show and Tell • Retelling short stories • Guided reading aloud • Alphabet and phonic games 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sentence completion activities • Reflection writing • Playing crossword puzzles • Oral sharing and retelling stories • Picture description • Word sorting activities • Essay writing • Story telling using comic strips 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflection writing • Oral sharing • Mini talk shows • Retelling stories • Storytelling with comic strips • Essay writing • Guided reading aloud • Audio recording • Word dorting activities • Sentence completion activities
Visual-Spatial Intelligence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Paper folding • Kinesthetic concepts • Hands-on thinking • Body maps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating simple dioramas • Using pictures and models • Graphic organizers (charts, maps, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating dioramas and 3D models • Tangram activities • Rubik's cube

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simple manipulatives (blocks and puzzles) • Creating simple posters or collages • Spot the difference games • Tracing shapes, letters and numbers • Crafting 3D Models 	<p>timelines, Venn diagrams)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tangram activities • Shape and pattern puzzles • Maze games 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shape, pattern, maze games • Collage making • Poster creation
Interpersonal Intelligence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Think-Pair Share • Small group collaborative activities • Buddy reading • Peer sharing of ideas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mini interviews with classmates • Mini talk shows • Peer teaching • Peer feedback • Group brainstorming 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Think-Pair-Share • Small group collaborative Activities • Peer teaching and feedback • Team games • Mini Interviews • Group brainstorming
Intrapersonal Intelligence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Writing a short diary or journal • “I can” statements • Color your Mood activity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Writing short journals or diaries • Creating scrapbooks or mini “All About Me” Books 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Journals • Dairies • Scrapbooks

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expressing emotions through drawings, colors, or words 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Designing simple photo albums with captions Reflecting on personal feelings and experiences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reflecting on personal feelings Goal setting “I am” statements Expressing emotions through drawings, colors or words
Logico-Mathematical Intelligence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number matching games Matching shapes and objects Simple graphing and pictographs Classifying and categorizing objects by shape, color or type Solving simple word problems in familiar contexts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Estimation activities Brain teasers and riddles Simple calculations Quantifying objects Comparing amounts Measuring Guided questioning to encourage logical thinking 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Solving word problems and tricky math questions Brain teasers Riddles Estimations and calculations Matching, classifying and categorizing objects Guided questioning to encourage logical thinking

2. The Department of Education and school administrators are encouraged to develop, implement, and facilitate teacher orientations, seminars, webinars, and training workshops. These capacity-building activities should focus in the variety of teaching methodologies, strategies, and learning activities in order to efficiently and effectively cater multiple intelligences in the teaching and learning process.

3. For pupils, they should be guided to recognize their multiple intelligences, develop their strengths, apply their intelligences in academic tasks and real-life situations. Furthermore, pupils are encouraged to engage in collaborative activities where they can confidently share their talents and learn from others, and they should set personal goals that will guide them in developing and strengthening their MI's and reaching their fullest potential.

4. For parents and guardians, they are encouraged to provide continuous support at home by maximizing the use of available resources such as televisions, smartphones, art and storybooks, Bible, musical instruments like guitars and pianos, as well as toys and games such as LEGO and board games. Their guidance and active involvement play a vital role in developing their children's interest, talents and multiple intelligences. Furthermore, they should allow their children to freely explore their interest and talents by providing opportunities and resources that are beneficial to the development of their MI's.

5. Teachers and parents should work hand in hand in guiding pupils' learning and overall development. Pupils MI can be developed and strengthened with consistent support, encouragement and active participation, both at home and at school. Thus, parents and teachers are encouraged to keep open communication and provide regular feedbacks on pupil's progress, needs and achievements to ensure continuous growth and development.

6. To future researchers who would conduct the same or related studies, they are encouraged to explore other factors that could influence multiple intelligences and academic performance, as well as to employ alternative techniques and assessments that can better capture the wide range of pupils' MI.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Prior to the conduct of the study, formal permission was secured from the proper authorities of Saint Ferdinand College, including approval from the President of the institution and the principal of the Elementary Department. Since the respondents were primary pupils, parental or guardian consent, as well as pupil assent, were obtained before the administration of the questionnaire and collection of academic records.

Participation in the study was voluntary, and the respondents were informed of the purpose and nature of the research. They were assured that non-participation or withdrawal from the study would not result in any penalty. Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly observed throughout the research process. All information gathered was used solely for academic purposes and handled with utmost care to protect the identity and privacy of the respondents.

Acknowledgements

The researcher is profoundly grateful to all who inspired, guided and supported her throughout this masteral journey. Words cannot fully express her appreciation for the encouragement, patience, and wisdom generously shared, which made the completion of this work possible.

To Dr. Marites P. Talosig, her thesis adviser, for her unwavering guidance, support, and invaluable advice from the very beginning until the completion of this thesis.

She extends her gratitude to Dr. Salome S. Cariño, Dr. Vilma C. Cabrera, and Dr. Charina G. Alejo, her thesis panelists, for their guidance, assistance, patience and valuable suggestions, which greatly contributed to the successful completion of this manuscript.

To Madam Josephine Marie L. Dela Cruz, her former Principal at SFC Elementary Department, for her guidance, encouragement, and support, which greatly helped in the successful completion of this study.

To Engr. Mario Q. Sevilla, her statistician, for his expert guidance and invaluable assistance in the statistical treatment of this study.

To Madam Benelyn P. Jamora, secretary, and Madam Maricel P. Ramos, OIC Dean of SFC Graduate School, for their patience and guide throughout this journey.

She is eternally grateful to her parents, Papa Pedro, Mama Angeles, for their love, care, understanding, sacrifices, and moral support, which strengthened her determination and inspired her to complete this study.

To her siblings, Ate She, Kuya Emman, and Ading Lester, for their steadfast support, constant encouragement, and reassuring reminders that every effort and challenge faced along this journey would ultimately be worthwhile.

And above all, the LORD ALMIGHTY for giving her and granting her the knowledge, wisdom, courage, patience, and determination to finish this thesis.

REFERENCES

- Ahvan, R., & Pour, Z. (2016). The correlation of multiple intelligences for the achievements of secondary students. ERIC. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1091511.pdf> (Accessed February 19, 2025)
- Armstrong, T. (2017). Multiple intelligences in the classroom (4th ed.). ASCD.
- Bautista, F. V. (2015). Multiple Intelligence of faculty and selected students in the College of Science: Input to faculty and student development program. University of Rizal System. Retrieved from <http://www.urs.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/2016/06/4737-12369-1-PB.pdf> (accessed February 20, 2025)
- Blasco-Magraner, J. S., Bernabe-Valero, G., Marin-Liebana, P., & Moret-Tatay, C. (2021). Effects of the educational use of music on 3-to-12-year-old children's emotional development: A systematic review. ResearchGate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/350545306_Effects_of_the_Education_al_Use_of_Music_on_3-to-12-Year-Old_Children's_Emotional_Development_A_Systematic_Review (Accessed January 28, 2026)
- Capinding, A. T. (2021). Academic performance among minority students in Dingalan National High School. ERIC. Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED611431.pdf> (accessed September 8, 2025)
- Da-anton, C. L. F., & Dioso, E. D. (2025). The effects of electronic gadgets on the learning behavior of students: A correlation. ResearchGate. Retrieved from

- https://www.researchgate.net/publication/394634375_The_Effects_of_Electronic_Gadgets_on_the_Learning_Behavior_of_Students_A_Correlation (accessed January 28, 2026)
- Dag, C., Turkkan, E., Kacar, A., & Dag, H. (2021). Children's only profession: Playing with toys. PMC. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8430366/> (Accessed September 6, 2025)
- Dela Cruz, K. G. (2013). A study on multiple intelligences and its relationship to the academic achievement of grade V pupils in selected schools in the Division of Olongapo City Academic Year 2012-2013. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14018890> (accessed February 13, 2025)
- Doblon, M. G. B. (2022). Senior high school student's multiple intelligences and their relationship with academic achievement in science. ResearchGate. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/368608405_Senior_High_School_Students'_Multiple_Intelligences_and_their_Relationship_with_Academic_Achievement_in_Science (accessed February 21, 2025)
- Ezeanwu, R. C., Ezeanwu, A. B., Okoro, J. O., & Onah, U. J. (2022). Availability and utilization of reading resources in homes for effective learning among primary school children. Zeenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.6946288> (Accessed September 6, 2025)
- Gardner, H. (2011). *Frames of mind: The theory of multiple intelligences* (3rd ed.). Basic Books.
- Gardner, H. (2013). Frequently asked questions—Multiple intelligences and related educational topics. Howard Gardner. Retrieved from https://howardgardner01.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2012/06/faq_march2013.pdf (accessed February 16, 2025)
- Harhatik, S., Istiningsih, G., Suryawan, A., & Purwandari, S. (2021). Multiple intelligences profile of grade IV elementary school students in Magelang. Atlantis Press. <https://www.atlantis-press.com/proceedings/bis-hss-21/125982547?> (Accessed January 28, 2026)
- Ibrahim, A. H. K., & Al Saeed, B. A. (2017). The relationship of multiple intelligences and their impact on the academic achievement of the students of the elementary school in Hawat Bani Tamim. *AJSRP Journals*. Retrieved from <https://journals.ajsrp.com/index.php/jeps/en/article/view/43> (accessed January 28, 2026)
- Limon, L. M. (2021). The multiple intelligence of the high school students of Saint Ferdinand College as basis for the selection of appropriate teaching strategies in mathematics (Unpublished thesis). St. Ferdinand College.
- Moral-Perez, M. E. D., Fernandes-Garcia, L. C., & Guzman-Duque, A. P. (2015). Videogames: Multisensory incentives boosting multiple intelligences in primary education. *Electronic Journal of Research in Educational Psychology*, 13(2), 243-270. Retrieved from <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1074117> (accessed October 31, 2025)
- Mufit, S. S. (2022). Investigating the relationship between multiple intelligences and perceptual learning styles of Turkish ELT students. Semantic Scholar. Retrieved

from <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:251353271> (accessed February 12, 2025)

- Nulhakim, L., & Berlian, L. (2020). Investigation of multiple intelligence of primary school students. *Jurnal Inovasi Pendidikan IPA*, 6(1), 101-113.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343042427_Investigation_of_multiple_intelligence_of_primary_school_students (Accessed February 12, 2025)
- Politimou, N., Stewart, L., Mullensiefen, D., & Franco, F. (2018). A novel instrument to assess the home musical environment in the early years. *PLOS ONE*. Retrieved from <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0193819> (accessed January 26, 2026)
- UNESCO. (2020). Education for sustainable development: A roadmap. UNESCO. Retrieved from <https://en.unesco.org/themes/education-sustainable-development>
- UNICEF. (2020). Inclusive education: A fundamental right for all children. UNICEF. Retrieved from <https://www.unicef.org/education/inclusive-education>
- Yavich, R., & Rotnitsky, I. (2020). Multiple intelligences and success in school studies. ERIC. Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1277917.pdf> (accessed February 11, 2025)